

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF SMALL BUSINESS SUBJECTS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the advantages and disadvantages of the digital economy in the development of small business and the establishment of electronic services based on theoretical and methodological approaches to digitization of the activities of small business entities and improvement of the field in the era of globalization and digital economy. Also, current issues of business process digitization are analyzed.

Key words: small business, infrastructure, innovation.

Introduction

Together with the fact that digital technologies include a complex process that leads to changes in the forms of organization of economic activity, it complicates the nature of events and, in turn, creates a hybrid world that can change them. Especially for business entities in today's globalization process, the period of transition to the digital economy provides them with ample opportunities to discover new approaches to managing business processes and create innovative products and services. Businessmen who are able to quickly change the management and service models of business entities in the digital economy are becoming the leaders of today's market reforms.

Literature analysis.

Today, the digital economy is the new economy for almost all countries. However, in countries such as the USA, China, and Japan, as a result of the widespread use of information and communication technologies, which have new opportunities for technological production and the industry, digitization of the business sector by transitioning to a digital economy has already been started. In this regard, many scientists have studied the theoretical aspects of digitalization of small business.

from the scientists of the CIS countries Y.I.Seliverstov, A.A.Rudichev, Y.A. Dmitriyeva's "Digital technologies are developing at an incredible speed, they are changing the nature of business processes in many ways, creating opportunities to increase production efficiency and reduce product costs," he said. [1].

European state scientists E. Rusliati and M. Mulyaningrum "The digital economy brings full benefits to the business sector (growth, productivity, competitiveness, wage workers, consumers. The digital economy enables rapid growth of income for many business sectors he said, interaction with developers also allows to facilitate the solution of transactional issues [2].

D. Makhmudova, one of the scientists of our country, on the importance of digitalization of small businesses, including business subjects, according to the definition "Digital business economy is the optimization of business processes as a result of the

application of techniques and technologies, innovations, and new business models and platforms are the direct driving force of the digital economy. " interpreted as [3].

Indeed, the definitions given by scientists and their theoretical foundations require digitization in the sphere of small business productivity and diversification in the conditions of today's globalization.

Research methodology

The study used economic, comparative, analytical and sample observation, statistical and forecasting and other methods.

Analysis and results

Increasing the level of competitiveness of enterprises of any form of ownership, including small businesses, as well as optimizing their activities in the face of intense competition, remains an urgent problem. A prerequisite for ensuring the competitiveness of small businesses is the high level of use of all tools available in them, such as modern technologies, innovations, quality of goods and services, management efficiency.

Small business is essentially a small entrepreneurial activity based on independent activity. French economist Andre Marshall (1907-1968) was one of the first to add a fourth factor to the three factors of production (land, capital, labor) - the factor of organization. Since then, the concept of entrepreneurship and the scope of work in this field have expanded.

The main goal of the entrepreneur is to determine the need for the product in order to acquire his customers. An entrepreneur should take into account the following main factors when forming his customers:

- novelty of the product and its compatibility with the buyer;
- quality of goods or services;
- price of goods or services;
- degree of universality of the product;
- the possibility of using after-sales services;
- compliance of the goods with accepted general or state standards;
- attractiveness of advertising of goods and services, attracting the attention of the

buyer, etc.

The principle of digital economy organization is based on the fact that today, many opportunities have been created to meet the needs of consumers through the virtual world, and the population's demand for using these opportunities is sufficient. From this point of view, digital transformation of small business entities is necessary.

Digital transformation of small businesses involves turning them into "digital enterprises" based on new business, economic and management principles based on digital technologies.

The possibilities of the digital economy are wide-ranging. In the conditions of globalization, the main opportunities of the digital economy are understood to be the electronic use of available opportunities at a distance. It can also be implemented through deep integration of information technologies in the field of production and service. The main aspect of the opportunities is the use of electronic business processes that can be served remotely with the effective use of financial technologies, remote services in meeting primary or secondary needs, online payments, online orders, online courier, information about the products of manufacturers. It is possible to use services such as obtaining data, buying goods

in exchange for digital currencies issued over the Internet, or using them in the provision of services.

Such opportunities provide great opportunities for small business entities to create a favorable environment.

According to A.M. Beloborodko, "In a broad sense, digitalization of small business in the digital economy means all economic activities based on digital technologies related to e-business and e-commerce, as well as all electronic goods and services produced and sold using new technologies." cited by rif [4].

In the conditions of the digital economy, business entities can organize digital services within the framework of their authority, which gives the opportunity to achieve the goal with the maximum benefit with minimal cost. For example, small business entities producing light industry can organize wholesale and retail trade through the Internet by implementing a site, platform or software based on digital e-business, in addition to selling their products wholesale to merchants. This increases the possibility of export across the country and even abroad as the volume of trade increases.

It also increases the effectiveness of establishing integrated communications between large and small production sites by establishing electronic production communication systems.

At this point, if we turn to the opinion of scientists, S. Aleksandrov and R. Iskandarov "Digital economy is an economy implemented with the help of digital telecommunications." In the development of small and medium-sized businesses, information is considered the main resource, it is a source that never ends and is used many times, and it is one of the main advantages of the digital economy [5].

The advantages and disadvantages of the digital economy are important in the digitization of small business. As can be seen from the theoretical data, the development of the digital economy affects the efficiency of small business activities, because the new digital models allow, first of all, to reduce costs and, as a result, get additional income from digital services, improve customer service infrastructures (Table 1).

Table 1

Advantages and disadvantages of the digital economy in small business development ¹

Advantages of the digital economy	
Providing information resources	Use of this resource is unlimited
Creation of sales areas on the Internet	Not limited
Successful competition	Among small business entities
Operational scope	It depends on the size of the Internet
Disadvantages of the digital economy	
IT professionals	Lack of specialists or low qualification of students in the digital economy

Digital economy is an economic activity that consists of digital data as the main factor of production and includes:

¹ Муаллиф ишланмаси

- 1) formation of information space taking into account the needs of society for high-quality and reliable information;
- 2) development of information infrastructure of the region, organization and application of information and telecommunication technologies;
- 3) creation of new technological foundations of the socio-economic sphere.

The infrastructure of the digital economy is the main criterion for using the opportunities of the digital economy in the development of small business. According to Yu.A. Oleynikova, "Digital infrastructure (English digital infrastructure) is a set of technologies and equipment that allows the formation of digital space, including computing and telecommunication capacities, digital markets, and electronic networks. It should be recognized that the digital infrastructure is one of the important components of the digital economy, as it provides digital networks for data transmission, the integration of machines and equipment, which allows to reduce the costs of equipment operation and user maintenance. Digital infrastructure capabilities are required to support existing processes, as well as to develop and improve new technologies. Digital thinking (English digital mind) refers to the ability of people to use digital technologies to solve existing and new problems, collect and analyze information, monitor consumer preferences, create solutions, communicate with customers and partners, etc. . As a result, the widespread development of digital thinking is aimed at forming a digital or "smart" society, in which the work of most specialists is related to information and knowledge management" [6].

The main goal of small business development in the conditions of the digital economy is that through the use of digital technologies, it allows small businesses to reduce costs, increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the enterprise, occupy certain positions in the market of digital goods and services, and produce new types of products.

Conclusion

In the conditions of the digital economy, business entities can organize digital services within the framework of their authority, which gives the opportunity to achieve the goal with the maximum benefit with minimal cost. For example, small business entities producing light industry can organize wholesale and retail trade through the Internet by implementing a site, platform or software based on digital e-business, in addition to selling their products wholesale to merchants. This increases the possibility of export across the country and even abroad as the volume of trade increases.

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